

Advances in Network Orchestration for Security, Scalability, and Sustainability

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Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive examination of orchestration technologies and emphasizes their importance for modern network management and IoT integration in Beyond 5G systems. After an introduction to orchestration and its taxonomy, we categorize orchestration into four key areas: Service Orchestration (SCO), Resource Orchestration (RO), Lifecycle Service Orchestration (LSO) and Security Orchestration (SO). Moreover, multi-domain orchestration details are provided in complex network environments. As a case study, we then focus on security orchestration in IoT for 5G technologies, reviewing existing methods and their effectiveness and highlighting gaps. Fundamental principles and technologies as well as current challenges and limitations in management and orchestration are analyzed, with particular attention to scalability, adaptability and security issues. The discussion concludes with an outlook on future research and development directions in the field of orchestration that address the new challenges in a rapidly changing technological landscape.

Index Terms—sustainability, network orchestration, network management, scalability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Orchestration is the automated arrangement and coordination of sophisticated networking resources, services, and systems [1]. It controls all systems, resources, and services automatically and with innate intelligence. Orchestration enables the E2E network service management and delivery over different technologies, domains, and operators with minimum human interaction. The research community has made significant progress in this area. However, there are still grey areas and unanswered questions. 5G and Beyond networks intend to revolutionize the telecommunication industry by creating a well-connected world through service classes such as uRLLC, mMTC, and eMBB. These service classes will require new infrastructure and a set of new technologies that can fulfil strict latency, reliability, and bandwidth specifications. Motivated by these challenges, the research community has come up with innovative technologies which increase scalability and flexibility while reducing the Operating Expenses (OPEX) and Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) [2]. SDN and NFV play a crucial role in the softwarization and virtualization of the network and integration of different technologies to work collaboratively and provide E2E services. There is a need for a controlling, monitoring, and management system to optimize the capabilities of these novel technologies and E2E architecture and maximize the Quality of Service (QoS) and reliability. This system mentioned above should be capable

of delivering the E2E services while abstracting, automating, and monitoring the available physical and virtual resources [3]. Network orchestration is recognized as these processes and coordinated activities. In [3], authors define orchestration as the process of automatically selecting and managing diverse resources, services, and systems to achieve predetermined objectives. These processes should be reliable, consistent, secure, timely, and less expensive due to automation and virtualization. Orchestration involves different service providers and operators who own the underlying resources. As stated in 3GPP Technical Specification 28.801 [4], orchestration analyses and renders a given service request into physical and virtual resource configuration as required for the service initiation. Resource provisioning policies or existing accessible resources may be employed when configuring resources.

For smooth operation and service delivery, it would be better if there was a method to separate the service layer, such as service slices, applications, and Operations Support System (OSS), from the low-level resource and management layers, such as Element Management Systems (EMS), controllers, and Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM). This separation will allow innovative services, resource optimization, and a more adaptable infrastructure for tailored service delivery. While taking the responsibility of decoupling the service layer and management and infrastructure layers, Through a single pane of glass for service creation, deployment, and operation, Network Service Orchestration (NSO) defines interactions between network services and resources and frameworks. NSO uses correctly specified programming interfaces, descriptors, and data models to introduce service abstractions. For example, NSO may connect traditional OSS and Business Support Systems (BSS) to Virtual Network Functions (VNF). Authors of [3] illustrate this relationship using a unifying tenet through the hourglass shape as in Figure 1 where the importance of NSO as an inter-working, technology-neutral glue between essential services and underlining management of resources is highlighted [3].

II. TAXONOMY OF ORCHESTRATION

NSO can be categorized into four main categories depending on their functional scope as shown in Figure 2. These are Service Orchestration (SO), Resource Orchestration (RO), Lifecycle Service Orchestration (LSO) and Security Orchestration (SCO) [3]. Each network service has a critical business

Fig. 1: Strategic role of the NSO.

value for its functionality [2]. The **SO** is responsible for provisioning, managing and optimising the network services. Once a service request is received, the service orchestrator must plan and execute a protocol that meets connectivity, reliability and E2E quality of service requirements. **SCO** can be seen as a higher level functionality that focuses on interacting with other network functions and infrastructure to dynamically execute all services and continuously adjust configurations while monitoring the performance of all network services. **RO** is responsible for allocating virtual and physical resources for service requests. In 5G, this allocation is performed by elements such as Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (NFVO), EMS and SDN controllers [3]. When creating a network service, the orchestration of the underlying infrastructure is the responsibility of RO. The infrastructure consists of different types of hardware and software as well as various hosting and connectivity functions. The resources include Extended Enhanced Platform Awareness (EEPA), storage, network and processing power [5]. The Metro Ethernet Forum (MEF) was founded for layers 2 and 3 standards, specifications, and verification procedures. It has defined **LSO** as follows. LSO is a nimble method for facilitating and sustainably automating the lifecycles of network services through coordinated administration and management across all network domains responsible for the delivery of E2E connectivity services such as Carrier Ethernet, Multi-Protocol Label Switching (MPLS) and Internet Protocol Virtual Private Network (IP VPN) [6]. LSO intends to automate and manage operations and connectivity services, including design, performance, analytics, policy functions, security, assurance, control and utilisation across the entire life-cycle of layer two and layer three. To deliver the E2E services, LSO works across all network systems that require coordinated management, governance and control [7]. **SCO** is responsible for the integration of all tools, technologies and underlying infrastructure to enable Security Automation (SA). IT, automation algorithms and AI are used in SA to detect, prevent and remediate cyberattacks automatically and without human intervention [8]. SCO is one of the four pillars of orchestration that plays a significant role in realizing zero-touch security in 5G and B5G networks.

Fig. 2: Different types of orchestrator functions

A. Multi-Domain Orchestration

A domain can be considered a network system governed by an administrator using a common set of rules with an overall view and access to its underlying resources [47]. Domains are defined based on the operator or service provider; given that multiple service providers are involved, it's called multi-domain. The network service orchestrator receives different kinds of service requests. When the network service orchestrator creates a service, the orchestration process can exceed the domain boundaries. For the E2E service delivery, there is a necessity to use services and resources of other service providers or operators. When the orchestration process confines to a single domain, it is single-domain orchestration, and when the orchestration process expands over multiple domains, it is multi-domain orchestration. NSO is supposed to handle single and multi-domain orchestration, providing E2E service delivery. In single-domain orchestration, the orchestrator has total control over all the services and resources available within its domain. It has an overview of the service and resource components, a clear understanding of the network capabilities of the domain, and complete authority over them. A domain orchestrator interacts with all the network components, such as computing, storage, and networking resources, while managing and controlling VNFs. Multi-domain orchestration includes orchestrating services and resources in multi-operator and multi-technological domains [1].

In multi-domain orchestration, local orchestrators do not have an overview or understanding of other operators' topologies, architecture, or resources. Therefore, multi-domain orchestration is more sophisticated, and it is necessary that underlying infrastructure and technologies support cross-information exchanges and interactions between different network providers/operators to provide smooth E2E services [48]. There is currently no standard for processing the exchange of information across multiple domains. In the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) NFV Release 2, two different architectures are proposed to tackle multi-domain orchestration [49]. One administrative domain consists of one or more data centres and VIMs. In the first case, the NFVO is divided into a network service orchestrator and a resource orchestrator. As shown in Figure 3 (a), the service orchestrator manages the network service, while the resource orchestrator provides an overview of all resources in the administrative domain. The network service orchestrator is not

TABLE I: FEATURES COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF ORCHESTRATION FUNCTIONS

Aspect	Service Orchestration	Resource Orchestration	Security Orchestration	Life-cycle Orchestration
Functionality	Service composition/decomposition, cooperation with other elements like OSS and BSS [2], [9]	Service requests for virtual and physical resources mapping present an abstract view of the resources available in the administrative domain [9].	Enable SA, orchestrate security activities, act as a middleware hub [8], [10]–[12]	Handling processes, dependencies, and workflows among service components, maintain services per the Service Level Agreements (SLA), allows for services' dynamic and on-demand creation, modification, and deletion. [2], [6], [7], [9]
Layer	Upper Layer/ Application Layer [9]	All layers [9]	All layers [9]	Layer 2 and 3 [7], [9].
Administrative domain	Single/ Multi [1], [9]	Single/ Multi [1], [9]	Single/ Multi [9]	Single/ Multi [1], [9]
Enabling technologies	SDN, NFV, Cloud computing, Service Function Chaining (SFC) [2], [7], [9]	SDN, NFV, Cloud computing [2], [7], [9]	SDN, NFV, Cloud/Edge/Fog Computing, Network slicing, Lightweight virtualization [10]–[18]	SDN, NFV, SFC [2], [7], [9]
Applications				
5G	Improve the mobile service creation, integration of different technologies, handling of traffic or subscriber congestion [9]	Resource utilization, dynamic resource allocation based on service requirements, allows flexible network resource management [2], [9], [19]	Zero-touch security monitoring and management, improve response time, satisfiability of Security Service Level Agreements (SSLA) for different use cases [10]–[12], [15]–[18]	Automate all of a slice's life cycle phases, including preparation, instantiation, configuration, activation, run time and decommissioning [19]
Data networks	Adapt and modify routes as needed, logical services implementation, traffic forwarding optimization [9]	Load reduction, dynamic allocation of resources according to traffic variation [9]	Ensure E2E security, virtualization security, self healing self repair networks [10], [11], [15]–[17]	Optimize and aggregate MPLS Label Switching Paths (LSP), micro-segmented pathways that can be programmed based on QoS, business policies, and security [9]
Data centres	Keep servers and in-network isolation for a wide range of customers, low latency and high throughput among data centres, network services integration in data centres and among data centres [9]	Program paths optimizing traffic workloads, load reduction on central processing units, provide an abstract view of underline resources [9]	Optimum resource allocation for security service while ensuring the QoS [10], [11], [15]–[17]	Guarantees of SLAs for distinct classes of traffic [9]
Network domains	Core network, Edge network, Radio Access Network (RAN), Device level, Cloud network [9]	Core network, Edge network, RAN, Cloud network [9]	Core network, Edge network, RAN, Device level, Cloud network [12]–[14], [16]–[18]	Core network, Edge network, RAN, Device level, Cloud network [9]
Existing implementations	Cisco Network Services Orchestrator [20], the HPE Service Director [21], Oracle Communications Network Service Orchestration Solution [22], Ericsson Orchestrator [23], Ericsson Dynamic Orchestration [24]	Ericsson orchestrator [23], OpenStack heat (OH) [25], Redzinc VELOX equipment manager [26]	McAfee, Swimlane [8]	Ericsson orchestrator [23], ESCAPE [27]
Standardization	ESTI [28], Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [29], Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN) [30], 3GPP [31], Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS) [32], Open Networking Foundation (ONF) [33], International Telecommunication Union (ITU) [34]	ESTI [28], Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [29], Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS) [32]	ESTI [35], [36], Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [29], Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) [37], [38]	ESTI [39], MEF [6]
Related projects	T-NOVA [40], 5GEx [41], SONATA [42], VITAL [43]	T-NOVA [40], 5GEx [41], SONATA [42], UNIFY [44], VITAL [43], 5G-Transformer [45]	Anastacia [46]	T-NOVA [40], VITAL [43], 5GEx [41], SONATA [42], 5G-Transformer [45]

aware of the resource status of the individual domains and only knows the resource capacity specified by the resource orchestrators of the individual domains. Here, the network operator can offer the infrastructure to different departments within the same operator and offer the infrastructure to different network operators if there are agreements to share the network. The service orchestrator and the VNF manager can be part of a different domain. In the second use case, as shown in Figure 3 (b), there is no split in the NFVO. However, a new reference point is introduced between the NFVOs. This method is referred to as the umbrella NFVO. The umbrella NFVO manages the lifecycle of the umbrella network services specified in this NFVO, but not the lifecycle of the network services available in each admin domain and managed by the

respective NFVO. It provides the management and onboarding of VNF packages and network service templates. Each administrative domain has VNF managers, associated VNFs and NFVOs. This domain NFVO performs standard operations that are restricted to its domain. In this case, too, similar objectives are pursued as in the first case. ESTI NFV release 3 [50] presents an architecture for multi-domain orchestration with NFV. As shown in Figure 3 (c), a new reference point called "Or-Or" is introduced to facilitate communication and interoperability between NFVOs. The domains are arranged in a hierarchy. In the scenario shown in Figure 3 (c), the NFVO in administrative domain C is at the top and performs the instantiation of composite network services provided by administrative domains A and B. NFVOs in different admin-

trative domains collaborate to initiate nested network services and initiate other lifecycle management operations such as scaling or healing the nested network services.

III. FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR SCALABILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

Supporting sustainability in network management and orchestration within a distributed environment involves considering a range of principles and technologies to minimize environmental impact and resource usage. Some metrics to measure sustainability, are: (i) *resource efficiency* measures the efficient use of resources (e.g., CPU, memory, energy) in the network management and orchestration system. Sustainability involves minimizing resource waste. (ii) *energy consumption* quantifies the energy consumption of the network management infrastructure and assesses its environmental impact. Sustainable solutions aim to minimize energy usage or use renewable energy sources. (iii) *cost-effectiveness* evaluates the cost implications of the network management solution, including initial setup costs, operational costs, and potential cost savings achieved through scalability and resource optimization. (iv) *environmental impact* assesses the carbon footprint and ecological impact of the network management and orchestration system. Sustainability often involves reducing carbon emissions and minimizing harm to the environment. (v) *longevity and adaptability* measures the ability of the system to evolve and adapt to changing network requirements and technologies over time, ensuring that investments in the system remain viable in the long term. (vi) *compliance and standards* evaluate whether the network management solution adheres to industry standards and best practices for sustainability, such as ISO 14001 for environmental management [51]. (vii) *user satisfaction* assesses the satisfaction of end-users and network operators with the system, as a sustainable solution should also meet the needs and expectations of stakeholders. (viii) *scalable sustainability* considers how sustainability measures are affected as the network scales. Ensure that sustainability efforts are not compromised as the network grows.

Some fundamental principles and technologies that can support sustainability are: (i) *Energy Efficiency*: Using energy-efficient data center designs, cooling systems, and power management technologies to reduce energy consumption and consolidating physical servers through virtualization to optimize resource utilization and reduce the number of physical machines in operation. Moreover, implementing dynamic resource allocation and power management strategies to scale resources based on demand reduces energy waste during periods of low usage. (ii) *Renewable Energy Sources*: Investing in or procuring renewable energy sources such as solar or wind power, to run data centers and network infrastructures to reduce dependence on fossil fuels. (iii) *Resource Recycling and Reuse*: Implementing e-waste management programs to responsibly dispose of or recycle obsolete network equipment and devices, and considering to reuse or repurpose hardware components whenever possible to extend their lifespan. (iv) *Efficient Network Design*: Optimizing network topology and

routing to minimize data transmission distances and reduce energy consumption and using techniques such as Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) to cache and serve content closer to end-users, reducing the need for long-distance data transfers. (v) *Software Optimization*: Writing efficient code and optimize software algorithms to reduce computational and memory requirements, leading to lower energy consumption and choosing network protocols and communication standards that prioritize energy efficiency. (vi) *Monitoring and Analytics*: Implementing real-time energy monitoring and management systems to track and optimize energy usage across network infrastructure. Conduct assessments to measure the environmental impact of network operations and identify areas for improvement. (vii) *Sustainable Procurement*: Source network equipment and components from environmentally responsible manufacturers and suppliers that adhere to sustainability standards. (viii) *Lifecycle Management*: Planning for the responsible disposal or recycling of network equipment when it reaches the end of its lifecycle and evaluating the environmental impact of network management and orchestration solutions over their entire lifecycle, including production, usage, and disposal. (ix) *Green Data Management*: Implementing data compression and deduplication techniques to reduce storage requirements and lower energy consumption for data storage. (x) *Collaborative Initiatives*: Participating in open-source projects and collaborate with industry initiatives focused on sustainable network management and orchestration solutions. (xi) *Regulatory Compliance*: Ensuring compliance with environmental regulations and standards related to energy efficiency and sustainability.

In terms of network management, self-sustaining networks can adapt to the dynamic and complex environment of new applications. For example, the migration from environmentally adaptive, self-organising networks to self-sustaining networks can maintain strict performance indicators. This transformation can be achieved through targeted distributed network management, network orchestration to automate lifecycle management workflows and the implementation of advanced architectures such as cell-free networks [52]. Automation, softwareization and intelligence in network management, inspired by frameworks such as Zero Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) and Experiential Network Intelligence (ENI) architectures, are also important to achieve sustainable networks.

IV. CHALLENGES AND INNOVATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE AND SCALABLE NETWORK MANAGEMENT

Implementing a scalable and sustainable network management solution can have a profound impact on the environment and energy efficiency when dealing with distributed network slices. By optimizing resource allocation, reducing energy consumption and promoting environmentally friendly practices, organizations can significantly reduce their environmental footprint. Sustainable solutions often favor the use of green data centers powered by renewable energy sources, which reduces the environmental impact associated with power generation. In addition, practices such as server virtualization, containerization and efficient code execution minimize

Fig. 3: Approaches adopted by ETSI for several administrative domains (a) The orchestrator is divided into two parts (NSO and RO); (b) Umbrella NFVO: Multiple orchestrators with a new reference point (c) Hierarchical approach with a new reference point Or-Or [49], [50]

the hardware and software resources required for network management, contributing to energy savings. This transition to clean energy, together with responsible disposal of appliances and green procurement, reduces the overall environmental impact of network operations. In addition, a holistic approach that assesses environmental impact across the entire network management lifecycle helps to identify opportunities for improvement, while regulatory compliance ensures adherence to energy efficiency and sustainability standards. Ultimately, companies that are committed to sustainability in network management not only reduce their ecological footprint, but also strengthen their public image as ecologically responsible companies and attract stakeholders and customers who are also committed to protecting the environment.

Current network management and orchestration solutions also face significant challenges and limitations when dealing with distributed network slices. One major challenge is the complexity of managing heterogeneous network resources and services spread across multiple geographic locations. Coordinating the allocation and optimization of resources for multiple network slices, each with its own requirements, can overwhelm existing orchestration systems. In addition, scalability becomes a pressing issue as the number of network slices multiplies, especially in 5G and 6G networks. Ensuring efficient resource utilization while avoiding overprovisioning or underutilization is difficult. In addition, the dynamic nature of network traffic and the need for real-time adaptability make it challenging to ensure consistent quality of service across distributed slices. Security and isolation issues are another limitation as protecting the integrity and privacy of network slices in a distributed environment becomes more complicated. As network slices extend to the edge and span resources from multiple vendors, achieving end-to-end security and seamless interoperability remains a significant hurdle. In addition, ensuring sustainability by optimizing resource allocation and energy efficiency is paramount, but existing solutions are often inadequate in terms of environmental performance. To overcome these challenges and limitations, future network management and

orchestration solutions must focus on automation, intelligence, and adaptability while addressing the environmental, security, and scalability implications of distributed network slices.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents an in-depth analysis of orchestration technologies, focusing on their taxonomy, applications in IoT within 5G networks and pressing challenges in terms of scalability, sustainability and security. By categorizing orchestration into SO, RO, LSO and SCO, the complexity and interdependencies of multi-domain orchestration systems become clear. The study on security orchestration in IoT for 5G technologies shows significant progress in existing approaches while highlighting the need for more robust, adaptable and efficient mechanisms to counter evolving threats. In addition, the fundamental principles, technologies and challenges of network management for complex networks emphasise the need to integrate innovative solutions that ensure resilience, scalability and environmental sustainability.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Guerzoni, I. Vaishnavi, D. Perez Caparros, A. Galis, F. Tusa, P. Monti, A. Sganbelluri, G. Biczók, B. Sonkoly, L. Toka *et al.*, “Analysis of end-to-end multi-domain management and orchestration frameworks for software defined infrastructures: an architectural survey,” *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 28, no. 4, p. e3103, 2017.

- [2] C. Rotsos, D. King, A. Farshad, J. Bird, L. Fawcett, N. Georgalas, M. Gunkel, K. Shiimoto, A. Wang, A. Mauthe *et al.*, "Network service orchestration standardization: A technology survey," *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, vol. 54, pp. 203–215, 2017.
- [3] N. F. S. de Sousa, D. A. L. Perez, R. V. Rosa, M. A. Santos, and C. E. Rothenberg, "Network service orchestration: A survey," *Computer Communications*, vol. 142, pp. 69–94, 2019.
- [4] 3GPP, "3gpp technical specification 28.801." [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3091>
- [5] J. Ordonez-Lucena, P. Ameigeiras, D. Lopez, J. J. Ramos-Munoz, J. Lorca, and J. Folgueira, "Network slicing for 5g with sdn/nfv: Concepts, architectures, and challenges," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 55, no. 5, pp. 80–87, 2017.
- [6] M. Forum, "Lifecycle Service Orchestration(LSO): Reference Architecture and Framework," University of Zurich, Department of Informatics, Tech. Rep., 01 2016.
- [7] G. Saadon, Y. Haddad, and N. Simoni, "A survey of application orchestration and oss in next-generation network management," *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, vol. 62, pp. 17–31, 2019.
- [8] C. Islam, M. A. Babar, and S. Nepal, "A multi-vocal review of security orchestration," *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 1–45, 2019.
- [9] N. F. Saraiva de Sousa, D. A. Lachos Perez, R. V. Rosa, M. A. Santos, and C. Esteve Rothenberg, "Network service orchestration: A survey," *arXiv e-prints*, pp. arXiv–1803, 2018.
- [10] A. Molina Zarca, J. Bernal Bernabe, I. Farris, Y. Khettab, T. Taleb, and A. Skarmeta, "Enhancing iot security through network softwarization and virtual security appliances," *International Journal of Network Management*, vol. 28, no. 5, p. e2038, 2018.
- [11] A. M. Zarca, J. B. Bernabe, R. Trapero, D. Rivera, J. Villalobos, A. Skarmeta, S. Bianchi, A. Zafeiropoulos, and P. Gouvas, "Security management architecture for nfv/sdn-aware iot systems," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 8005–8020, 2019.
- [12] P. Ranaweera, V. N. Imrith, M. Liyanag, and A. D. Jurcut, "Security as a service platform leveraging multi-access edge computing infrastructure provisions," in *ICC 2020-2020 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [13] E. Jalalpour, M. Ghaznavi, D. Migault, S. Preda, M. Pourzandi, and R. Boutaba, "A security orchestration system for cdn edge servers," in *2018 4th IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization and Workshops (NetSoft)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 46–54.
- [14] A. Molina Zarca, D. Garcia-Carrillo, J. Bernal Bernabe, J. Ortiz, R. Marin-Perez, and A. Skarmeta, "Enabling virtual aaa management in sdn-based iot networks," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 2, p. 295, 2019.
- [15] A. Hermosilla, A. M. Zarca, J. B. Bernabe, J. Ortiz, and A. Skarmeta, "Security orchestration and enforcement in nfv/sdn-aware uav deployments," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 131 779–131 795, 2020.
- [16] A. Molina Zarca, M. Baga, J. Bernal Bernabe, T. Taleb, and A. F. Skarmeta, "Semantic-aware security orchestration in sdn/nfv-enabled iot systems," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 13, p. 3622, 2020.
- [17] A. M. Zarca, J. B. Bernabe, A. Skarmeta, and J. M. A. Calero, "Virtual iot honeynets to mitigate cyberattacks in sdn/nfv-enabled iot networks," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 1262–1277, 2020.
- [18] J. Ortiz, R. Sanchez-Iborra, J. B. Bernabe, A. Skarmeta, C. Benzaid, T. Taleb, P. Alemany, R. Muñoz, R. Vilalta, C. Gaber *et al.*, "Inspire-5gplus: Intelligent security and pervasive trust for 5g and beyond networks," in *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security*, 2020, pp. 1–10.
- [19] I. Afolabi, T. Taleb, K. Samdanis, A. Ksentini, and H. Flinck, "Network slicing and softwarization: A survey on principles, enabling technologies, and solutions," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 2429–2453, 2018.
- [20] "Cisco network services orchestrator - cisco network services orchestrator data sheet," Oct 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/products/collateral/cloud-systems-management/network-services-orchestrator/datasheet-c78-734576.html>
- [21] "Hewlett packard enterprise simplifies nfv operations for communications service providers." [Online]. Available: <https://www.hp.com/us-en/hp-news/press-release.html?id=2158374#.YdtHUVmxWbg>
- [22] [Online]. Available: <https://www.oracle.com/us/industries/communications/service-network-orchestration-ds-3764076.pdf>
- [23] [Online]. Available: <https://www.ericsson.com/en/portfolio/digital-services/automated-network-operations/orchestration/ericsson-orchestrator>
- [24] [Online]. Available: <https://www.ericsson.com/en/portfolio/digital-services/automated-network-operations/orchestration/dynamic-orchestration>
- [25] "Heat." [Online]. Available: <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Heat>
- [26] "Realtime video telemedicine solutions - redzinc services," May 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://redzinc.net/>
- [27] A. Csoma, B. Sonkoly, L. Csikor, F. Németh, A. Gulyás, W. Tavernier, and S. Sahhaf, "Escape: Extensible service chain prototyping environment using mininet, click, netconf and pox," *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 125–126, 2014.
- [28] [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-IFA/001_099/010/02_03.01_60/gs_NFV-IFA010v020301p.pdf
- [29] "Internet engineering task force (ietf)." [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc7491.txt>
- [30] [Online]. Available: https://www.ngmn.org/wp-content/uploads/Publications/2019/190312_5G_Network_and_Service_Management_including_Orchestration_3.14.0.pdf
- [31] [Online]. Available: <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3090>
- [32] "Tosca; introduction." [Online]. Available: <http://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/tosca-nfv/v1.0/tosca-nfv-v1.0.html>
- [33] [Online]. Available: https://opennetworking.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/TR-540_Orchestration-_A_More_Holistic_View_1.50.47_PM.pdf
- [34] "T recommendations." [Online]. Available: <https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/recommendations/rec.aspx?rec=13350&lang=en>
- [35] S. Dahmen-Lhuissier, "Experiential networked intelligence (eni)." [Online]. Available: <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/experiential-networked-intelligence>
- [36] —, "Zsm." [Online]. Available: <https://www.etsi.org/committee/zsm>
- [37] "Ieee p1915.1 security in virtualized environments." [Online]. Available: <https://site.ieee.org/p1915-1-sve/>
- [38] "P1917.1 - standard for software defined networking and network function virtualization reliability." [Online]. Available: https://standards.ieee.org/project/1917_1.html
- [39] [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-IFA/001_099/010/02_03.01_60/gs_NFV-IFA010v020301p.pdf
- [40] "Nova project website: T-nova, fp7, ict, network functions virtualisation." [Online]. Available: <http://www.t-nova.eu/>
- [41] "5gex." [Online]. Available: <https://5g-ppp.eu/5gex/>
- [42] "Agile development, testing and orchestration of services in 5g virtualized networks." [Online]. Available: <https://www.sonata-nfv.eu/>
- [43] "Home," Oct 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.vital5g.eu/>
- [44] [Online]. Available: <https://www.eict.de/projekte/#project-23>
- [45] "Transformer.eu." [Online]. Available: <http://5g-transformer.eu/>
- [46] A. P. Consortium, accessed on 27.07.2021. [Online]. Available: <http://www.anastacia-h2020.eu/>
- [47] M. A. S. Santos, A. Ranjbar, G. Biczók, B. Martini, and F. Paolucci, "Security requirements for multi-operator virtualized network and service orchestration for 5g," in *Guide to Security in SDN and NFV*. Springer, 2017, pp. 253–272.
- [48] R. V. Rosa, M. A. S. Santos, and C. E. Rothenberg, "Md2-nfv: The case for multi-domain distributed network functions virtualization," in *2015 International Conference and Workshops on Networked Systems (NetSys)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 1–5.
- [49] N. F. Virtualisation, "Etsi industry specification group (isg),"etsi gs nfv-man 001 v1. 1.1: Network functions virtualisation (nfv); management and orchestration," 2014.
- [50] —, "Etsi industry specification group (isg),"etsi gs nfv-man 001 v1. 1.1: Network functions virtualisation (nfv); management and orchestration," 2018.
- [51] W. L. Kuhre *et al.*, *ISO 14001 Certification: Environmental Management System*. Prentice Hall, 2018.
- [52] A. Mämmelä, I. Ahmad, M. M. Mowla, A. Flizikowski, M. A. B. Abbasi, D. Zelenchuk, and M. Sinaie, "Sustainability in 6g networks: Vision and directions," 2022.